

AN ADAPTIVE MULTI-POPULATION EVOLUTIONARY ALGORITHM FOR CONTAMINATION SOURCE IDENTIFICATION IN WATER DISTRIBUTION SYSTEMS

Changhe Li¹, Rui Yang², Li Zhou³, Sanyou Zeng⁴, Michalis Mavrovouniotis⁵, Ming Yang⁶,
Shengxiang Yang⁷, and Min Wu⁸

¹Professor, School of Automation, China University of Geosciences, Wuhan 430074, China;
and Hubei Key Laboratory of Advanced Control and Intelligent Automation for Complex
Systems, Wuhan 430074, China(corresponding author). Email: changhe.lw@gmail.com

²School of Automation, China University of Geosciences, Wuhan 430074, China. Email:
2280920465@qq.com

³School of Automation, China University of Geosciences, Wuhan 430074, China. Email:
441837060@qq.com

⁴Professor, School of Mechanical Engineering and Electronic Information, China University
of Geosciences, Wuhan 430074, China. Email: sanyouzeng@gmail.com

⁵KIOS Research and Innovation Center of Excellence, Department of Electrical and
Computer Engineering, University of Cyprus, Nicosia, Cyprus. Email:
mavrovouniotis.michalis@ucy.ac.cy

⁶Associate Professor, School of Computer Science, China University of Geosciences, Wuhan
430074, China. Email: mingyang@cug.edu.cn

⁷Centre for Computational Intelligence (CCI), School of Computer Science and
Informatics, De Montfort University, Leicester LE1 9BH, U. K. Email: syang@dmu.ac.uk

⁸Professor, School of Automation, China University of Geosciences, Wuhan 430074, China;
and Hubei Key Laboratory of Advanced Control and Intelligent Automation for Complex
Systems, Wuhan 430074, China. Email: wumin@cug.edu.cn

ABSTRACT

Real-time monitoring of drinking water in a water distribution system (WDS) can effectively warn and reduce safety risks. One of the challenges is to identify the contamination source through these observed data due to the real-time, non-uniqueness, and large scale characteristics. To address the real-time and non-uniqueness challenges, we propose an adaptive multi-population evolutionary optimization algorithm to determine the real-time characteristics of contamination sources, where each population aims to locate and track a different global optimum. The algorithm adaptively adjusts the number of populations using a feed-back learning mechanism. To effectively locate an optimal solution for a population, a co-evolutionary strategy is used to identify the location and the injection profile separately. Experimental results on three WDS networks show that the proposed algorithm is competitive in comparison with three other state-of-the-art evolutionary algorithms.

Keywords: Multi-population adaptation, dynamic bilevel optimization, evolutionary computation, contamination source identification

1 INTRODUCTION

2 Water distribution systems (WDSs) are highly susceptible to various threat attempts, in-
3 cluding uncertain natural disasters, deliberate destruction, and system failures. For example,
4 a contamination source injected into a WDS will spread through the system rapidly and ex-
5 pose the people to health risks. Detection of the contamination in a WDS using sensors could
6 yield useful observations to identify and locate such contamination threat events. Based on
7 these observations, we can deduce the location, initiation time, and historical injection rate
8 by solving an inverse problem with an optimization algorithm given the observation data
9 under a water distribution simulation model. Because of the rapid diffusion of contaminants
10 in a WDS, we should identify the source characterizations quickly and accurately.

11 The problem is challenging due to the real-time, non-uniqueness/multi-modal, large-
12 scale, and expensive characteristics. The real-time property requires the search to be data-
13 driven, i.e., the search starts immediately after the contamination is detected at any sensor,

14 and continuously adapts to changes when new observation data come. The non-uniqueness
15 means that more than one solutions conform to the observation data, which requires the
16 algorithm to have the capability of searching more than one solution simultaneously. The
17 large scale property means that the search space will increase exponentially due to the
18 increase of the number of dimensions of the vector of the injection rate as observation data
19 increase. The problem will become expensive to simulate when the scale of the network
20 increases. There are mainly three kinds of methods for the identification of contamination
21 source in WDSs, including the particle inversion method (Zierolf et al. 1998; Laird et al.
22 2005; Shang et al. 2002; Costa et al. 2013), the machine learning method (Perelman and
23 Ostfeld 2013; Taormina and Galelli 2018; Huang and Mcbean 2009; Yang et al. 2011), and
24 the simulation-optimization method (Guan et al. 2006; Liu et al. 2008; Seth et al. 2016; Hu
25 et al. 2015). The first two methods can only deduce the location of the contamination source,
26 while the third method can deduce all the information of a contamination event. Therefore,
27 the simulation-optimization method is adopted in this paper.

28 To address the real-time and non-uniqueness challenges, we propose a new adaptive multi-
29 population evolutionary algorithm where the water distribution network model is coupled
30 directly with a dynamic bilevel optimization model to evaluate solutions as new observa-
31 tion data come. To address the non-uniqueness difficulty, we incorporate a multi-population
32 method where each population aims to locate a different solution, and the number of pop-
33 ulations is adaptively adjusted to adapt to the increase of observation data by a feed-back
34 learning mechanism and hence to identify alternative solutions as many as possible. The
35 population diversity across all network nodes will be adaptively increased according to the
36 evolving state of populations measured by a node covering ratio. Thus, at any stage of the
37 observation event, possible solutions that best conform to the observations are identified.
38 In order to speed up the search for a possible solution, in each population, a cooperative
39 co-evolutionary strategy is proposed to locate the location and historical injection rate sep-
40 arately. Experiments in this paper are based on an EPANET 2.0 model (Rossman 2000) of

41 the water distribution network. Experimental results on three different networks show that
42 the proposed algorithm outperforms several other peer algorithms.

43 The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 briefly reviews the related
44 work. Section 3 presents a simulation-optimization model for the problem and introduces
45 our proposed method. Section 4 presents experimental results on three networks. Finally,
46 conclusions and future work are given in Section 5.

47 RELATED WORK

48 In this section, we focus on the review of simulation-optimization methods, which can be
49 classified into three categories according to the optimization method used. These algorithms
50 include the gradient descent (GD) method, the particle swarm optimization (PSO) , and the
51 genetic algorithm (GA).

52 The basic idea of a GD method is to use the gradient direction of the current position as
53 the search direction. Guan et al. (2006) adopted the gradient descent method as the search
54 operator to solve the problem of locating pipe network contamination sources based on the
55 simulation-optimization model. Xin et al. (2013) got the locally optimal solution according
56 to the direction of gradient descent search. In this method, when approaching the optimal
57 value, the convergence speed will gradually slow down, that is, the closer to the objective
58 value, the step length will be smaller, and even causes a zigzag drop.

59 The genetic algorithm is based on the Darwinian evolution of “survival of the fittest”. In
60 the literature, several papers (Preis and Ostfeld 2008; Preis and Ostfeld 2006; Sreepathi et al.
61 2007) used GAs to solve the problem and achieved promising results. Cristo et al. (2008),
62 firstly established the potential node-set representing the solution of pollution sources – water
63 contamination matrix, then used a GA to search the optimal solution. Yan et al. (2016) used
64 a hybrid encoding method to code the contaminant source identification problem according
65 to the properties of a variable, and combined the crossover and mutation operations. Sankary
66 et al. (2018) proposed a framework to obtain monitoring data by placing mobile sensors using
67 an adaptive GA.

68 The PSO, which is a swarm intelligence method, originated from the study of the flocking
69 behavior of birds simulating their behavior of flying and foraging in groups. Guneshwor et
70 al. (2018) proposed a simulation-optimization model by using a radial point collocation
71 method and the PSO to identify the unknown groundwater contaminant sources. In this
72 method, due to the lack of dynamic adjustment of particle velocity, it is easy to fall into
73 local optima. Besides the above search algorithms, an evolution strategy algorithm based on
74 a Gaussian mutation operator (GD-ES) was proposed to generate new individuals (Zechman
75 and Ranjithan 2009), and an elite graduation selection strategy was introduced to determine
76 the offspring.

77 From 2008 to 2011, Liu et al. (2008, 2010, 2011) proposed a multi-population method
78 with GA, which uses an adaptive dynamic optimization technology (ADOT) to make a
79 real-time response to injection events to locate contamination sources. To overcome the
80 premature convergence issue, the algorithm (Liu and Ranjithan 2010) starts with a large
81 number of randomly generated populations and removes populations that are close to each
82 other during the optimization process. A diversity-driven mechanism is used to increase the
83 population diversity for the survival selection in the later evolution stage. The algorithm
84 achieves a great performance in comparison with other optimization algorithms, but it still
85 lacks the mechanism to search the spaces that are not covered by any population at the
86 global level. The number of populations only decreases as time goes on. This issue will be
87 addressed in this paper.

88 In addition to the literature on contamination source identification described above, there
89 are some important studies on the use of evolutionary algorithms to determine the optimal
90 locations of sensors and the developing an early warning system. Ostfeld and Salomons
91 (2004) presented a method for finding the optimal layout of an early warning detection
92 system. In the next year, Ostfeld and Salomons (2005) extended their previous work by
93 a introducing uncertainties to the demands and injected contamination events. Berry et
94 al. (2006) introduced a mixed-integer programming method for sensor placement. In the

95 same year, Propato (2006) formulated a mixed-integer linear programming model to identify
 96 optimal sensor locations for early warning against accidental and intentional contaminations.
 97 Olikar and Ostfeld (2014) improved the event-detection ability by including the support
 98 vector machine for the detection of outliers and a multivariate analysis for examining the
 99 relationship between water-quality parameters and their mutual patterns.

100 METHODOLOGY

101 An inverse problem can be constructed to identify the contamination source character-
 102 istics, where the input is a set of concentration observations at sensors and the objective is
 103 to minimize the error between predicted concentration and actual observation at sensors on
 104 the network using a water distribution simulation model.

105 Simulation-optimization Model

106 The simulation-optimization model has two sub-models: a simulation model and an
 107 optimization model. The simulation model mainly describes the water movement in a WDS,
 108 including the water flow model and the solute transport model. The optimization model
 109 can transform the problem into an optimization problem of describing the location of the
 110 contamination source, the injection start time, and the injection history information.

The water flow model and water quality model in urban common water supply network can be realized by the hydraulic simulation function of water quality in EPANET 2.0. The model can simulate the diffusion of solutes in contamination events and feedback of node concentration data. We define

$$y_j(t) = \mu(\mathbf{x}(t)), j = 1, \dots, K \quad (1)$$

111 where $y_j(t)$ denotes the concentration data of contaminants detected by sensor j at time
 112 step t (each sensor is set at a different node); $\mathbf{x}(t) = (x_u, \mathbf{x}_l(t))$ denotes information of a
 113 contamination event at a single source at time step t , $x_u \in \mathbb{N}$ denotes the location of the
 114 contamination source; $\mathbf{x}_l(t) = (x_0, x_{x_0}, x_{x_0+1}, \dots, x_t) \in \mathbb{R}^{t-x_0+2}$ denotes the injection profile,

115 where x_0 is the starting time and $(x_{x_0}, x_{x_0+1}, \dots, x_t)$ is a time series of injection rate from
 116 x_0 to t ; μ is a simulation model of water distribution systems with the input $\mathbf{x}(t)$ and the
 117 observed output $\mathbf{y}(t)$ of K sensors.

118 Given the water quality hydraulic simulation model, the problem of locating and tracing
 119 contamination sources can be converted into a dynamic bilevel optimization problem. The
 120 upper-level optimization task is to find the location (x_u) of a contamination event, and the
 121 lower-level task is to find the injection history profile ($\mathbf{x}_l(t)$), which is defined as a dynamic
 122 optimization problem whose variables will increase as time goes on. Note that, the problem
 123 is defined as a single-level optimization problem in previous work discussed in Section 2.
 124 In our experiments, we found that the location variable has a significant influence on the
 125 distribution of the objective value and the injection profile variables do not. Therefore, we
 126 divide the problem into two levels and solve them cooperatively.

In this paper, the square root of the mean squared error between the observed data of
 a possible solution and the actual observed data of contamination sources is used as the
 objective, which is shown below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \min_{x_u, \mathbf{x}_l(t)} \quad & f_u(x_u, \mathbf{x}_l(t)) = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{j=1}^K \sum_{s=0}^t [y_j(s) - \check{y}_j(s)]^2}{K \cdot t}} \\
 \text{s.t.} \quad & \mathbf{x}_l(t) \in \arg \min_{\mathbf{x}_l(t)} \{f_l(x_u, \mathbf{x}_l(t))\}
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

127 where $\check{y}_j(s)$ denotes the observed data at sensor j at time step s of the actual contamination
 128 source. Therefore, the objective is to minimize the cumulated error over all sensors so far
 129 since the initial observed data are obtained, i.e., to find a solution that complies with the
 130 actual observation data. The two levels of problems all aim to minimize the prediction error
 131 but have different tasks. In this paper, we solve the problem in an online manner under a
 132 real-world scenario.

133 As mentioned above, the problem is difficult due to the real-time, non-uniqueness, large
 134 scale, and expensive properties. For a typical WDS, the number of sensors is far less than the

135 number of nodes in the network due to the cost reason, which leads to the incompleteness
136 of the observation data and causes many global optima of Eq. (2) at a time during the
137 optimization process. It is a typical multi-modal optimization problem, and hence, multi-
138 modal optimization techniques are needed to find as many global optima as possible for
139 decision-makers to decide the actual one.

140 For the real-time property, the contamination source identification needs to start once
141 contaminants are detected immediately. With the increase of the observation data, the input
142 of the objective function will continuously change, which may cause the optimal solution set
143 to change. Therefore, it is necessary to identify the optimal solution location in real-time
144 when solving the problem, that is, to solve the problem with dynamic optimization method,
145 to ensure that the source information can be obtained in time when the contamination event
146 occurs.

147 The large-scale property couples with the expensive property. There are mainly three
148 aspects to be considered. Firstly, when the scale of a WDS is quite large, the simulation
149 time of evaluating a solution will become unaffordable (i.e., it becomes expensive), and the
150 value range of the location of x_u will be increased sharply, resulting in a sharp increase in
151 solution space. Secondly, the dimension for historical contamination injection rate of \mathbf{x}_l will
152 increase as the contamination event keeps on. As the dimension of \mathbf{x}_l increases linearly,
153 the solution space increases exponentially, which makes it challenging for an algorithm to
154 find the optimal solution. Thirdly, when multiple contamination sources exist, the solution
155 representation becomes multiple time series, which makes the problem much more difficult
156 to solve.

157 In this paper, we mainly focus on addressing the former two considerations in a network
158 with a single contamination source. To address them, we propose an adaptive multiple
159 population framework to find multiple global solutions and adaptively adjust the number of
160 populations to adapt to the changes in observed data.

161 **Adaptive Multi-population Algorithm**

162 Multi-population (MP) methods are very efficient for tracking and locating multiple
163 optima in dynamic environments. This section presents the details of the adaptive multi-
164 population (AMP) framework proposed in this paper.

165 *Algorithm Framework*

166 The framework has three basic components: clustering, parallel search, and diversity
167 increasing components. Figure 1 shows the framework, where m is the size of a population
168 (fixed in the paper), $k(T)$ is the total number of populations at time T (a counter that keeps
169 the number of times the diversity increasing component is triggered after clustering), $\tilde{k}(T)$
170 is the number of populations survived after the parallel searching, and $\Delta k(T)$ is the number
171 of population to be added.

172 Algorithm 1 presents the pseudo-code of the framework of the adaptive multi-population
173 algorithm. The framework starts with a set of randomly initialized individuals at $T=0$, then
174 clusters these new individuals to a set of populations. Populations simultaneously search for
175 global optima and merge if their best individuals locate at the same node on the network.
176 When the coverage ratio over all nodes does not change over two successive generations, it
177 will trigger the diversity increasing procedure where a feedback learning method is used to
178 control the number of populations to be added.

179 *Generation of Multiple Populations*

180 The idea of *divide-and-conquer* is adapted to make each population search for different
181 regions, which is equivalent to reducing the search area of each population. For this purpose,
182 the k -means clustering method is adopted in this paper to generate multiple populations
183 whose search areas are not overlapping with each other.

We firstly generate a certain number of individuals at node i with a probability p_i , which
is the same ($p_i = 1/n$, n is the number of nodes of a network) for all nodes at the beginning

Algorithm 1: Pseudo-code of the adaptive multi-population framework

```
Set  $T \leftarrow 0$ ;  
Randomly initialize  $k(T) * m$  solutions;  
while new observation data are detected do  
    Clustering newly generated solutions;  
    while coverage ratio changes do  
        Cooperatively co-evolve each population by GL (Xia and Li 2016) and  
        SaDE (Qin et al. 2009) for one iteration;  
        if the best solutions of more than one population cover the same node then  
            Merge these populations by the competition mechanism;  
        Update the coverage ratio on the whole network;  
    Update the node selection probability by Eq. (3);  
    Estimate the number of populations ( $\Delta k(T)$ ) to be increased by Eq. (5);  
    Generate  $\Delta k(T) \cdot m$  solutions on the network according to the probability  
    obtained by Eq. (3);  
     $T \leftarrow T + 1$ ;
```

of a run and is updated before the increase of populations by:

$$p_i(T) = 1 - \frac{\sum_{s=0}^T \kappa_i(s)}{\max_{i \in n} \sum_{s=0}^T \kappa_i(s)} \quad (3)$$

184 where $\kappa_i(s)$ is the accumulated times of node i visited by individuals since the start of the run.
185 From Eq. (3), we can see that the more times a node is visited, the smaller the probability
186 of being selected when generating new solutions. For example, if a node has never been
187 visited by any individuals, the probability of being chosen will be one when generating new
188 solutions.

189 After that, the nodes covered by all new individuals are then clustered by the k -means
190 clustering method. Algorithm 2 shows the procedures of the k -means clustering method,
191 where the estimation of the number of clusters $\Delta k(T)$ to be clustered will be given later
192 in Section 3. Eventually, individuals of a cluster consist of a new population. Note that
193 the shortest distance of two nodes across the network can be used instead of the Euclidean
194 distance used in this paper.

Algorithm 2: Pseudo-code of the k -means clustering

```
Initialize  $\Delta k$  cluster centers;  
while clusters do not converge, i.e., cluster centers are still changing do  
  for each node do  
    Calculate the Euclidean distance from the node to each cluster center;  
    The node is assigned to the cluster whose center is nearest to the node;  
  Recalculate the center of each cluster;
```

195 *Cooperative Co-evolutionary Search*

196 The representation of the solution to the problem is composed of discrete and continuous
197 parts. The location variable is an integer, and the injection profile is represented by a vector
198 of real values. To alleviate the difficulty in searching the solution of the hybrid representation,
199 we use the cooperative co-evolution (CC) strategy (Potter and De Jong 1994) to solve the
200 upper-level and lower-level problems separately.

201 *Cooperative Co-evolution*

202 Cooperative co-evolution (Potter and De Jong 1994; Yang et al. 2017) is an extension of
203 the traditional evolutionary algorithm inspired by the strategy of *divide-and-conquer* when
204 dealing with large scale optimization problems. By decomposing decision variables into a
205 set of independent groups (each group of variables consists of a subproblem), the original
206 problem can be solved by solving these subproblems by different algorithms. We use two
207 different single-population based algorithms to solve the two levels problems using the CC
208 strategy, i.e., when evaluating a solution in one population, the value of the remaining
209 information is taken from the best solution of the other population.

210 *Genetic Learning*

211 Genetic learning (GL) (Xia and Li 2016) is an optimization method based on probability
212 and statistics. It consists of two components: gene prediction and gene exploration. The
213 gene prediction uses a probability model build on historical data to select genes, and the
214 gene exploration attempts to discover new genes to increase the population diversity. These
215 two components interact to form a feedback system. The genetic learning method makes

Algorithm 3: Pseudo-code of the genetics learning algorithm

```
for each individual do  
     $idx \leftarrow$  node index of the current individual;  
     $obj \leftarrow$  prediction error of the current individual;  
     $sum\_obj_{idx} \leftarrow sum\_obj_{idx} + obj$ ;  
     $count_{idx} \leftarrow count_{idx} + 1$ ;
```

216 full use of the historical information generated in the iteration process. It analyses the
217 fitness of each individual in every possible value of each decision variable and calculates the
218 probability of each value being selected. It then performs the mutation operation in each
219 dimension according to these probabilities.

We use this method to find the injection location of the upper-level problem. For each population, we count the cumulative prediction objective value sum_obj of each node in the network. Algorithm 3 shows the specific steps. The probability of node idx to be selected can be obtained by:

$$p_{idx} = \frac{mean_{max} - mean_{idx}}{\sum_{i=1}^n mean_{max} - mean_{idx}} \quad (4)$$

220 where $mean_{idx} = sum_obj_{idx}/count_{idx}$, $mean_{max} = \max(mean_i \mid i = 1, 2, \dots, n)$. The
221 probability will be updated every iteration. The nodes with smaller errors have larger prob-
222 abilities to be selected for GL.

223 *Strategy Adaptation Differential Evolution*

224 Differential evolution (DE) (Storn and Price 1997) is a simple yet effective optimization
225 algorithm, especially for solving continuous optimization problems. The strategy adaptive
226 differential evolution algorithm (SaDE) (Qin et al. 2009) is an enhanced version, where
227 the differential operators are selected adaptively according to their performance in previous
228 generations. Here four classical difference operators $DE/rand/1$, $DE/best/1$, $DE/target-to-$
229 $best/1$ and $DE/best/2$ are used to optimize the initial time and historical injection rate.
230 Note that the recommended values for parameters of SaDE (Qin et al. 2009) were used in
231 this paper.

232 *Population Management*

233 Population removal and population increase are two critical components of the adaptive
234 multi-population framework, especially in dynamic environments (Yang and Li 2010; Li and
235 Yang 2012; Li et al. 2015). The population removal component aims to remove redundant
236 populations, and hence to save computational resources. The population increase component
237 aims to increase the diversity in the areas which have not been searched or not sufficiently
238 searched so far, and hence to find more global optima solutions.

239 *Population Removal*

240 After the clustering, each population will cover a unique search area containing one or
241 several geographically closed nodes on the network. As the search goes on, some of the
242 populations may move toward the same area, and finally, converge at the same node of that
243 area. This causes redundant search, which should be prevented. To prevent more than
244 one population from searching in the same area, we check their best solutions. When their
245 best solutions locate at the same node on the network, these populations are deemed to be
246 overcrowded.

247 To address the overcrowding issue, we introduced a competition mechanism. When two
248 or more populations overcrowd in one area, they will compete with each other. We first
249 merge all overcrowding populations in that area, then rank all individuals of the combined
250 population according to the objective value, finally keep the best m individuals and remove
251 the remaining. The overcrowding detection is performed every iteration, and the competition
252 mechanism will be triggered whenever overcrowding populations are detected.

253 *Population Increase*

254 Increasing populations means increasing the diversity for exploring unexplored areas.
255 However, to increase populations, we need to know when, how many, and where to generate
256 new random solutions.

257 The moment to increase populations has a significant impact on the performance of
258 an algorithm in dynamic environments (Li et al. 2015). Frequently increasing the diversity

259 causes the inefficiency issue in the exploitation of global optima, while infrequently increasing
 260 the diversity causes the algorithm to fail to track the changes of the optima. In order to
 261 solve this problem, we increase populations when all populations enter into a stable status
 262 on the network indicated by the coverage ratio over all nodes, i.e., we increase populations
 263 when the coverage ratio does not change over two successive iterations.

After the identification of the moment to increase populations, the next step is to determine how many populations to be increased. Inspired by (Li et al. 2016), we propose a feedback learning strategy based on historical data to estimate the number of populations to be increased. After the detection of the moment to increase populations, we record the number of populations ($\tilde{k}(T)$) survived from the competition, then compare the reduced number with the previous increased number ($\Delta k(T - 1)$), which is set to $k(T = 0)/2$ initially. If the reduced number is less than the previous increased number, which is a positive feedback and means that new areas have been discovered, then the current increased number will be increased by one based on the previous increased number ($\Delta k(T - 1)$); if the reduced number is greater than the previous increased number, which is a negative feedback and the current increased number will be decreased by one based on the previous increased number; otherwise, there is no change:

$$\Delta k(T) = \begin{cases} \Delta k(T - 1) + 1 & \text{if } \Delta k(T - 1) < k(T) - \tilde{k}(T) \\ \max(\Delta k(T - 1) - 1, 1) & \text{if } \Delta k(T - 1) > k(T) - \tilde{k}(T) \\ \Delta k(T - 1) & \text{if } \Delta k(T - 1) = k(T) - \tilde{k}(T) \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

264 Note that, there is at least one population to be increased in the negative feedback case to
 265 make sure that finding new global optima is always possible.

266 Finally, we can generate random solutions to increase the population diversity. Different
 267 from the traditional random immigrant scheme where new solutions are uniformly randomly
 268 generated at all nodes without considering the distribution of the current and historical
 269 solutions on the network, we generate new solutions at node i with probability p_i obtained

270 by Eq. (3). This way, infrequently visited nodes have large probabilities of being explored,
271 which is very helpful for finding new global optima.

272 Note that, in order to respond to changes in dynamic environments, change detection is
273 usually needed, or an algorithm is directly informed at the moment when a change occurs. For
274 example, the algorithm (Liu et al. 2011) is informed once new data come, and mutation step
275 lengths are reinitialized. In this paper, we do not need to detect changes. Here, to respond to
276 changes, the population increase is determined only based on the current evolutionary status
277 of the whole populations but not necessarily at the moment of a change occurring, i.e., the
278 distribution of all solutions on the network does not changes means that the algorithm
279 becomes converging and needs to be diversified to enhance the exploration capability.

280 **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

281 In this section, we conduct two groups of experiments to study the performance of the
282 proposed algorithm. The first group of experiments aims to analyze the effect of the critical
283 parameters on the performance of our algorithm, including the initial number of populations
284 k and the size of a single population m . The second group of experiments aims to compare
285 the performance of our algorithm with several state-of-the-art evolutionary algorithms.

286 **Experimental Setup**

287 Our algorithm treats the water distribution network as a “black box”, the structure of the
288 networks has little impact on the performance of the algorithm. When the scale of a WDS
289 is quite large, the simulation time of evaluating a solution will become unaffordable, and the
290 value range of the location will be increased sharply, resulting in a sharp increase in solution
291 space. As a result, the algorithm performance may deteriorate. Then we take scales of the
292 networks as main factor influencing the performance of algorithms.

293 Three networks were chosen with the scale from 97 nodes to 430 nodes, as shown in
294 Figure 2. The configuration of each network is shown in Table 1, where the sensor nodes
295 were set according to the literature in the way that they can cover as many nodes as possible

296 during the injection events. For each network, we set three different test cases, which are
297 listed in Table 2, where the injection rate changes every 10 minutes.

298 In the experiments, the simulation duration was set to 24 hours, and observation data
299 were collected from sensors every 10 minutes. Given the above configurations in Table 2,
300 we assume that the range of $[0h, 4h]$ for the start time and $[5g, 30g]$ for the injection mass.
301 Therefore, new solutions are randomly initialized within these ranges. To reduce the com-
302 plexity of the problem, we assume the injection duration is known for all algorithms in this
303 paper. All the results in this paper are averaged over 20 independent runs, and each test
304 case was run for 200,000 objective evaluations.

305 Before the experiments, we conduct the hydraulic simulation for three water distribution
306 network, we analyzed the water age of all nodes, and concluded that if the pollutants were
307 injected at the water source, it can reach at each node during the simulation. We set sensors
308 according to the locations provided by literature and our experience to make the coverage of
309 the sensor as large as possible. Therefore, the occurrence of injection events can be detected
310 within the simulation time even if some sensors are in low-flow zones.

311 We use a success rate and the prediction error to evaluate the performance of an algo-
312 rithm. A successful run is a run where the true injection node is found, so the success rate is
313 the number of successful runs over the total number of runs. Note that, the prediction error
314 is averaged over all successful runs, not over the total number of runs in this paper.

315 **Parameter Sensitivity Analysis**

316 In this subsection, network 1 with configuration 1-3 in Table 2 was used to test the
317 performance change of our algorithm with different combinations of $k \in \{10, 20, 40\}$ and
318 $m \in \{20, 50, 100\}$, where each combination is listed in Table 3.

319 As shown in Table 4, the success rate is one regardless of the change in the size of a
320 single population and the initial number of populations. The prediction error varies a little
321 with different combinations. Figure 3 shows the change in the coverage rate and the number
322 of populations on instance 1-3 of network 1 with a fixed single population size of $m=50$,

323 where the initial number of populations is set to $k=10/20/40$ from left to right. From the
324 figure, it can be seen that the number of the diversity increase during the run is the same
325 (i.e, five times) and the number of populations finally survived is maintained at all about
326 nine. It indicates that the initial number of populations has no significant impact on the
327 performance of the proposed algorithm. Due to the adaptation mechanism, the number
328 of populations will be adjusted to an appropriate number for a specific problem. For the
329 following experiments, the default initial number of populations is set to 20.

330 Figure 4 shows the change in the coverage rate and the number of populations on instance
331 1-3 of network 1 with a fixed initial number of populations of 20, where the size of a single
332 population is set to $m=20/50/100$ from left to right. For the instance 1-3-4 with $m=20$,
333 compared with the instance 1-3-5 with $m=50$, the size of the overall populations is not enough
334 to explore the whole search space. Therefore, the algorithm will frequently increase new
335 populations to make up for the lack of the overall population size to improve its exploration
336 capability. When $m=100$, the population size is enough for the problem, and the frequency
337 of adding new population becomes low, which saves unnecessary computational overhead.
338 Similarly, it can also be seen that the different sizes of a single population have no significant
339 impact on the performance of the algorithm due to the diversity trigger mechanism. For a
340 small size, more new populations will be added to achieve the best exploration capability
341 and vice versa.

342 **Comparison with Other Algorithms**

343 In this subsection, three state-of-the-art simulation-optimization-based algorithms are
344 chosen to compare with our algorithm, named AMP-CC(GL-SaDE) for short. The peer al-
345 gorithms are ADOT-CC(GL-SaDE) (Liu et al. 2011), GD-ES (Zechman and Ranjithan 2009),
346 and LRM-ADOT-CC(GL-SaDE) (Liu et al. 2012). Both ADOT-CC(GL-SaDE) and LRM-
347 ADOT-CC(GL-SaDE) use an adaptive dynamic optimization technique based on multi-
348 populations. The differences is that LRM-ADOT-CC(GL-SaDE) uses a logistic regression
349 to predict the possible location of an injection event. GD-ES (Zechman and Ranjithan 2009)

350 uses evolution strategies (ESs) implemented with a tree-based encoding to represent variable-
 351 length decision variables. Note that, in order to compare the performance of the adaptive
 352 framework proposed in this paper with the one used in ADOT-CC(GL-SaDE) (Liu et al.
 353 2011) and LRM-ADOT-CC(GL-SaDE) (Liu et al. 2012), we use the same search method
 354 for each population (the cooperative co-evolutionary algorithm introduced in Section 3) for
 355 these three algorithms. The suggested parameter values were used for all the other three al-
 356 gorithms. Besides, the number of objective evaluations and consumed time for optimization
 357 are equivalent among our algorithm and three state-of-the-art algorithms.

358 *Comparison of the Success Rate and Prediction Error*

359 Table 5 shows the comparison of the success rate obtained by the four algorithms on
 360 each test instance where the best result of each instance is shown in bold font. It can be
 361 seen that AMP-CC(GL-SaDE) outperforms all the other three algorithms on five out of nine
 362 instances. AMP-CC(GL-SaDE) achieves a success rate of one on five out of nine instances
 363 and a minimum success rate of 0.9 on the other instances. For simple test instances with a
 364 short injection history, all the four algorithms can find the true location for all runs except
 365 GD-ES on instances of networks 2 and 3. However, when the injection profile increases, the
 366 performance of all the algorithms becomes worse. Compared with ADOT-CC(GL-SaDE),
 367 LRM-ADOT-CC(GL-SaDE) does improve the success rate due to the location prediction
 368 mechanism.

369 Table 6 presents the comparison of the prediction error obtained by all the four algorithms
 370 on all the test instances where the best result of each instance is shown in bold font. In
 371 each test case, the Wilcoxon rank sum test at a significant level of 0.05 is performed on
 372 the prediction error between our algorithm and other peer algorithms. The errors with
 373 suffixes +, −, or \approx indicate that the prediction errors obtained by other peer algorithms
 374 are significantly better than, significantly worse than, and statistically equivalent to our
 375 algorithm, respectively.

376 From Table 6, it can be seen that AMP-CC(GL-SaDE) outperforms all the other three

377 algorithms on all test instances. The performance of AMP-CC(GL-SaDE) is significantly bet-
378 ter than the other three algorithms on instances 1-1, 2-1, 2-2, and 3-3. The error achieved
379 by GD-ES is the worst among all the algorithms on small scale instances (networks 1 and 2).
380 LRM-ADOT-CC(GL-SaDE) introduces a pre-screening mechanism based on a logical regres-
381 sion model, which improves the performance on the small instances of networks 1 and 2, but
382 not on the large instances of network 3. Due to the adaptation of the number of populations,
383 AMP-CC(GL-SaDE) achieves much smaller errors than ADOT-based algorithms.

384 To test the impact of changing the total number of objective evaluations on the per-
385 formance of the four algorithms, we run all the algorithms on instance 1-3 with different
386 maximum numbers of objective evaluations. Figure 5 presents the comparison of the num-
387 ber of populations obtained when the run finishes and the average best prediction error of
388 each algorithm under different maximum numbers of evaluations on the test instance 1-3.
389 From the comparison, we can have (1) AMP-CC(GL-SaDE) achieves the largest number of
390 populations and it is always superior to other algorithms in terms of the prediction error and
391 (2) the advantage of multi-population methods over single population methods can also be
392 seen in the comparison, where all the errors obtained by the three multi-population methods
393 decrease when the maximum number of objective evaluations increases.

394 *Comparison of the Diversity Maintaining*

395 Figure 6 presents the comparison of the change in the coverage ratio and the number of
396 populations for the four algorithms on instances 1-3 (sub-figures on the top) and 3-1 (sub-
397 figures on the bottom). To some extent, the change in the coverage ratio during the runtime
398 reflects the exploring capability of an algorithm, i.e., the ability to maintain the population
399 diversity. Among the four algorithms, only GD-ES does not consider the population diversity.
400 In Figure 6, the coverage ratio of GD-ES sharply drops to a low level even at the beginning
401 of the run and maintains at that low level till the end of the run on both test instances. This
402 may results in a premature convergence issue since the problem is highly multi-modal, which
403 can explain the reason for the lower success rate of GD-ES than the other three algorithms.

404 The improvement of diversity is the key to improve the success rate of the algorithm, so
405 how to increase diversity will directly affect the ability to find optimal solutions. ADOT-
406 CC(GL-SaDE), LRM-ADOT-CC(GL-SaDE), and AMP-CC(GL-SaDE) all adopt the same
407 search methods but use different multi-population frameworks. AMP-CC(GL-SaDE) uses
408 the AMP framework proposed in this paper, and the other two use the ADOT framework
409 (Liu et al. 2011). The essential difference between the two frameworks is the mechanism of
410 increasing diversity. The ADOT framework uses a distance evaluation strategy to disperse
411 individuals in the population to other regions, but it does not increase the coverage ratio
412 as necessary. It is because ADOT does not increase individuals, but move them to other
413 nodes already covered by existing solutions. This can be validated from the coverage ratio of
414 ADOT-CC(GL-SaDE) and LRM-ADOT-CC(GL-SaDE) in Figure 6. Although this strategy
415 increases the exploring ability to a certain extent, it does not expand the scope of exploration
416 in essence, and its ability to search for new optima is not strong enough, which leads to the
417 lower success rate in comparison with the AMP framework.

418 From the two curves of AMP-CC(GL-SaDE) on instance 1-3 in Figure 6 (the top right),
419 it can be seen that when the coverage ratio remains for several iterations, the number of
420 populations increases and the coverage ratio rises sharply to nearly one. At this moment,
421 AMP-CC(GL-SaDE) expands the exploring area to the whole network. The AMP framework
422 increases the population diversity at the global level, while the ADOT framework increases
423 the population diversity at the local level within each population. Therefore, the exploring
424 capability of the AMP framework is much stronger than that of the ADOT framework.

425 Moreover, in the AMP framework, new solutions are initialized in the areas, where no
426 solution is covering, with a very large probability. During the runtime, the number of times
427 for each node visited by solutions is recorded. The more times the node is visited, the more
428 computing resources are spent at that node to optimize the injection history. However,
429 when new solutions are added, more computing resources are placed at the nodes with a few
430 visitors to find more global optima.

431 Different from the behavior of AMP-CC(GL-SaDE) on instance 1-3, the algorithm does
432 not increase populations during the whole run on instance 3-1, i.e., the diversity increasing
433 component is not triggered (similar to the ADOT framework). The scale of the network 3 is
434 much larger than that of network 1. Although the lowest level of the coverage ratio is similar
435 in the two cases, the number of nodes covered on instance 3-1 is much larger than that on
436 instance 1-3. This means that for the same given number of individuals, the population
437 diversity on instance 3-1 is also much larger than that on instance 1-3. Therefore, given a
438 limited evaluation budget, the algorithm spends more computing resources on exploiting the
439 current area rather than exploring new areas and tries to improve its performance on the
440 optimization of the historical injection profile. The comparison in the two scenarios shows
441 that the AMP framework can adapt to problems with different scales.

442 *Comparison of the Injection Profile*

443 Figure 7 shows the time-varying mean of contaminants concentrations observed at four
444 detection points on instance 1-3, where the solid red curve refers to the actual observation
445 data, the solid dark curve refers to the contaminants concentrations simulated by the best
446 solution found by the algorithms, and the gray dashed curves are for the remaining solutions.
447 It can be seen that the general trend of the dark solid curves are very close to the actual
448 data, i.e., the optimal solutions found by the algorithms are sound. Compared with the
449 other three algorithms, AMP-CC(GL-SaDE) finds more optimal solutions. The comparison
450 further verifies that AMP-CC(GL-SaDE) has stronger exploring capability than the other
451 three algorithms.

452 When we observe the change in the prediction error of the best solutions obtained by the
453 four algorithms in Figure 8, all the three multi-population based algorithms can quickly locate
454 the injection event in the beginning of the run except GD-ES. However, it is interesting to
455 observe that the performance of the three algorithms deteriorates when the new observation
456 data keep coming. The prediction errors of both ADOT-CC(GL-SaDE) and LRM-ADOT-
457 CC(GL-SaDE) are even worse than that of GD-ES after the number of evaluations reaches

30,000. Among the four algorithms, AMP-CC(GL-SaDE) achieves the minimal error for most of the running time.

Performance Investigation on Dynamic Contamination Sources

In this subsection, we identify dynamic contamination sources by our algorithm. To make sure that there is enough time for distributing the injected masses, the simulation duration was set to 48 hours, and observation data were collected from sensors every 10 minutes, other parameters of our algorithm were set as above. However, the location of the contamination source changes every six hours. Network 1 with four contamination sources change was used to test the performance by our algorithm. The injection rate of four sources was all set to 30,25,20,15,10,5,5,10,15,20,25,30 for simplicity. Considering that the current water quality of the water distribution network will be affected by the contamination sources in the previous stages, in our algorithm. Each simulation is from the beginning to the current time phase. In each stage, when a sensor detects that the contamination exceeds a certain threshold, the algorithm starts to optimize and search for the optimal location and injection rate of the pollution source in the current stage.

Table 7 shows the errors and success rates over 20 runs. The success rate of finding the real contamination source in each stage is 0.95, 1, 1 and 1. It can be seen that our algorithm also works well for dynamic contamination sources and can accurately find the real sources at each stage. The prediction error is shown in Figure 9. There are three peaks in the figure, because when the pollution source changes, the optimal solution of the existing population is no longer the global optimal solution, and the error will suddenly increase. However, the error quickly drops due to the parallel search ability of the proposed algorithm. Figure 10 shows the time-varying mean of contaminants concentrations observed at four detection points of one single run, where the solid red curve refers to the actual observation data, the solid dark curve refers to the contaminants concentrations simulated by the best solution found by the algorithm in terms of the error, and the gray dashed curves are for the remaining two best solutions. It can be seen that that there are four peaks during the runtime, which means

485 there are four different sources of pollution, and our algorithm can track the optimal solution
486 well.

487 **CONCLUSIONS**

488 This paper proposes an adaptive multi-population framework to solve the contamination
489 source identification problem in the water distribution system. The problem is defined as a
490 dynamic bilevel optimization problem. To handle the real-time and non-uniqueness charac-
491 teristics of the problem, we develop an adaptive mechanism to enhance the exploring ability
492 of multi-population methods and a cooperative co-evolution strategy for the bilevel opti-
493 mization problem. The AMP framework can automatically remove redundant populations
494 and adds a proper number of populations at a proper moment, which makes it adaptable to
495 different problems.

496 From the experimental results, we can draw the following two conclusions. Firstly, the
497 multi-population based methods have advantages over single-population based algorithms.
498 Secondly, by removing crowding populations in over-exploited areas and adding new popu-
499 lations in unexplored areas, the AMP framework can find more candidate solutions than the
500 ADOT framework. As a result, it significantly improves the success rate in finding the true
501 optimal solution.

502 We want to pursue the following work in the future. Firstly, more uncertain factors
503 should be considered during the simulation, e.g., network structures and the sensor locations.
504 Secondly, multiple contamination sources should also be considered in a dynamic scenario.
505 Thirdly, the simulation of large scale problems is very time-expensive, which is challenging
506 to simulation-optimization based methods. Finally, the number and the location of sensors
507 on the network is also an interesting topic.

508 **DATA AVAILABILITY**

509 Some or all data, models, or code generated or used during the study are available in a
510 repository online in accordance with funder data retention policies.

511 The source code for all the involved algorithms in this paper will be released in OFEC,
512 which is an open framework for evolutionary computation, at the link [https://github.](https://github.com/Changhe160/OFEC)
513 [com/Changhe160/OFEC](https://github.com/Changhe160/OFEC).

514 **ACKNOWLEDGMENTS**

515 This work was supported in part by the National Natural Science Foundation of China
516 under Grants 61673355, 61673331, and 62076226, in part by the Fundamental Research
517 Funds for the Central Universities China University of Geosciences (Wuhan) under Grants
518 CUG170603 and CUGGC02, in part by the Hubei Provincial Natural Science Foundation of
519 China under Grant 2015CFA010, in part by the 111 project under Grant B17040, in part
520 by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant
521 agreement No. 739551 (KIOS CoE) and from the Government of the Republic of Cyprus
522 through the Directorate General for European Programmes, Coordination and Development.

523 **REFERENCES**

- 524 Berry, J., Hart, W., Phillips, C., Uber, J., and Watson, J. (2006). “Sensor placement in
525 municipal water networks with temporal integer programming models.” *Journal of Water*
526 *Resources Planning & Management*, 132(4), p. 218–224.
- 527 Costa, D. M., Melo, L. F., and Martins, F. G. (2013). “Localization of contamination sources
528 in drinking water distribution systems: A method based on successive positive readings of
529 sensors.” *Water Resources Management*, 27(13), 4623–4635.
- 530 Cristo, C. D. and Leopardi, A. (2008). “Pollution source identification of accidental con-
531 tamination in water distribution networks.” *Journal of Water Resources Planning and*
532 *Management*, 134(2), 197–202.
- 533 Guan, J., Aral, M. M., Maslia, M. L., and Grayman, W. M. (2006). “Identification of contam-
534 inant sources in water distribution systems using simulation-optimization method: Case
535 study.” *Journal of Water Resources Planning and Management*, 132(4), 252–262.
- 536 Guneshwor, L., Eldho, T. I., and Kumar, A. V. (2018). “Identification of groundwater con-

537 tamination sources using meshfree rpcm simulation and particle swarm optimization.”
538 *Water Resources Management*, 32(4), 1517–1538.

539 Hu, C., Zhao, J., Yan, X., Zeng, D., and Guo, S. (2015). “A map reduce based parallel niche
540 genetic algorithm for contaminant source identification in water distribution network.” *Ad
541 Hoc Networks*, 35(DEC.), 116–126.

542 Huang, J. J. and Mcbean, E. A. (2009). “Data mining to identify contaminant event locations
543 in water distribution systems.” *Journal of Water Resources Planning and Management*,
544 135(6), 466–474.

545 Laird, C. D., Biegler, L. T., Waanders, B. G. V. B., and Bartlett, R. A. (2005). “Contam-
546 ination source determination for water networks.” *Journal of Water Resources Planning
547 and Management*, 131(2), 125–134.

548 Li, C., Nguyen, T. T., Yang, M., Mavrovouniotis, M., and Yang, S. (2016). “An adaptive
549 multipopulation framework for locating and tracking multiple optima.” *IEEE Transactions
550 on Evolutionary Computation*, 20(4), 590–605.

551 Li, C., Nguyen, T. T., Yang, M., Yang, S., and Zeng, S. (2015). “Multi-population methods in
552 unconstrained continuous dynamic environments: The challenges.” *Information Sciences*,
553 296, 95–118.

554 Li, C. and Yang, S. (2012). “A general framework of multipopulation methods with clustering
555 in undetectable dynamic environments.” *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computa-
556 tion*, 16(4), 556–577.

557 Liu, L. and Ranjithan, S. R. (2010). “An adaptive optimization technique for dynamic envi-
558 ronments.” *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, 23(5), 772–779.

559 Liu, L., Ranjithan, S. R., and Mahinthakumar, G. (2011). “Contamination source identifi-
560 cation in water distribution systems using an adaptive dynamic optimization procedure.”
561 *Journal of Water Resources Planning and Management*, 137(2), 183–192.

562 Liu, L., Zechman, E. M., Brill, Jr, E. D., Mahinthakumar, G., Ranjithan, S., and Uber, J.
563 (2008). “Adaptive contamination source identification in water distribution systems using

564 an evolutionary algorithm-based dynamic optimization procedure.” *Water Distribution*
565 *Systems Analysis Symposium 2006*, 1–9.

566 Liu, L., Zechman, E. M., Mahinthakumar, G., and Ranji Ranjithan, S. (2012). “Identifying
567 contaminant sources for water distribution systems using a hybrid method.” *Civil Engi-*
568 *neering and Environmental Systems*, 29(2), 123–136.

569 Olikier, N. and Ostfeld, A. (2014). “A coupled classification - evolutionary optimization model
570 for contamination event detection in water distribution systems.” *Water Research*, 51, 234–
571 245.

572 Ostfeld, A. and Salomons, E. (2004). “Optimal layout of early warning detection stations for
573 water distribution systems security.” *Journal of Water Resources Planning and Manage-*
574 *ment*, 130(5), 377–385.

575 Ostfeld, A. and Salomons, E. (2005). “Optimal early warning monitoring system layout
576 for water networks security: inclusion of sensors sensitivities and response delays.” *Civil*
577 *Engineering and Environmental Systems*, 22(3), 151–169.

578 Perelman, L. and Ostfeld, A. (2013). “Bayesian networks for source intrusion detection.”
579 *Journal of Water Resources Planning and Management*, 139(4), 426–432.

580 Potter, M. A. and De Jong, K. A. (1994). “A cooperative coevolutionary approach to function
581 optimization.” *Parallel Problem Solving from Nature (PPSN)*, 249–257.

582 Preis, A. and Ostfeld, A. (2006). “Contamination source identification in water systems: A
583 hybrid model trees-linear programming scheme.” *Journal of Water Resources Planning*
584 *and Management*, 132(4), 263–273.

585 Preis, A. and Ostfeld, A. (2008). “Genetic algorithm for contaminant source characterization
586 using imperfect sensors.” *Civil Engineering and Environmental Systems*, 25(1), 29–39.

587 Propato, M. (2006). “Contamination warning in water networks: General mixed-integer linear
588 models for sensor location design.” *Journal of Water Resources Planning & Management*,
589 132(4), p. 225–233.

590 Qin, A. K., Huang, V. L., and Suganthan, P. N. (2009). “Differential evolution algorithm

591 with strategy adaptation for global numerical optimization.” *IEEE Transactions on Evo-*
592 *lutionary Computation*, 13(2), 398–417.

593 Rossman, L. A. (2000). “Epanet 2 users’ manual.” *Report no.*, U. S. Environmental Protection
594 Agency.

595 Sankary, N. and Ostfeld, A. (2018). “Multiobjective optimization of inline mobile and fixed
596 wireless sensor networks under conditions of demand uncertainty.” *Journal of Water Re-*
597 *sources Planning and Management*, 144(8), 04018043.

598 Seth, A., Klise, K. A., Siirola, J. D., Haxton, T., and Laird, C. D. (2016). “Testing contam-
599 ination source identification methods for water distribution networks.” *Journal of Water*
600 *Resources Planning & Management*, 142(4), 04016001.1–04016001.11.

601 Shang, F., Uber, J. G., and Polycarpou, M. M. (2002). “Particle backtracking algorithm
602 for water distribution system analysis.” *Journal of Environmental Engineering*, 128(5),
603 441–450.

604 Sreepathi, S., Mahinthakumar, K., Zechman, E., Ranjithan, R., Brill, D., Ma, X., and
605 Von Laszewski, G. (2007). “Cyberinfrastructure for contamination source characteriza-
606 tion in water distribution systems.” *International Conference on Computational Science*,
607 Springer, 1058–1065.

608 Storn, R. and Price, K. (1997). “Differential evolution—a simple and efficient heuristic for
609 global optimization over continuous spaces.” *Journal of global optimization*, 11(4), 341–
610 359.

611 Taormina, R. and Galelli, S. (2018). “Deep-learning approach to the detection and localiza-
612 tion of cyber-physical attacks on water distribution systems.” *Journal of Water Resources*
613 *Planning and Management*, 144(10), 04018065.

614 Xia, Y. and Li, C. (2016). “Memory-based statistical learning for the travelling salesman
615 problem.” *2016 IEEE Congress on Evolutionary Computation (CEC)*, IEEE, 2935–2941.

616 Xin, K., Sheng, X., Tao, T., and Xiang, N. (2013). “Contamination source identification
617 in water distribution networks based on negative gradient method.” *Journal of Tongji*

618 *University*, 41(1), 116–120.

619 Yan, X., Zhao, J., Hu, C., and Wu, Q. (2016). “Contaminant source identification in water
620 distribution network based on hybrid encoding.” *Journal of Computational Methods in
621 Sciences and Engineering*, 16(2), 379–390.

622 Yang, M., Omidvar, M., Li, C., Li, X., Cai, Z., Kazimipour, B., and Yao, X. (2017). “Efficient
623 resource allocation in cooperative co-evolution for large-scale global optimization.” *IEEE
624 Transactions on Evolutionary Computation*, 21(4), 493–505.

625 Yang, S. and Li, C. (2010). “A clustering particle swarm optimizer for locating and tracking
626 multiple optima in dynamic environments.” *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Compu-
627 tation*, 14(6), 959–974.

628 Yang, X., Boccelli, D. L., and De Sanctis, A. E. (2011). “A bayesian approach for probabilistic
629 contamination source identification.” *World Environmental and Water Resources Congress
630 2011: Bearing Knowledge for Sustainability*, American Society of Civil Engineers, 304–313.

631 Zechman, E. M. and Ranjithan, S. R. (2009). “Evolutionary computation-based methods
632 for characterizing contaminant sources in a water distribution system.” *Journal of Water
633 Resources Planning and Management*, 135(5), 334–343.

634 Zierolf, M. L., Polycarpou, M. M., and Uber, J. G. (1998). “Development and autocalibration
635 of an input-output model of chlorine transport in drinking water distribution systems.”
636 *IEEE transactions on control systems technology*, 6(4), 543–553.

637 **List of Tables**

638 1 Network configurations 30

639 2 Configurations for nine test instances 31

640 3 Combinations of the initial number of populations (k) and the population size

641 (m) for test instance 1-3 in Table 2 32

642 4 Success rates and prediction errors of different combinations of k and m on

643 network 1 with configuration 1-3 33

644 5 Success rate of all the four algorithms in all the test cases 34

645 6 Prediction error and standard deviation of all the four algorithms in all the

646 test cases 35

647 7 Results of dynamic sources over 20 runs on network 1 36

TABLE 1. Network configurations

Network	# of nodes	# of sensors	Sensor location
1	97	4	113, 147, 211, 120
2	279	12	J-124, J-202, J-204, J-196, J-122, J-267, J-115, J-197, J-14, J-55, J-3, J-58
3	430	16	J-56, J-321, J-296, J-11, J-258, J-209, J-118, J-345, J-112, J-121, J-69, J-171, J-200, J-6, J-342, J-229

TABLE 2. Configurations for nine test instances

Instance	Location	Start time	Duration (min)	Injection rate	
Network 1	1-1	113	0:00	60	5,10,15,20,15,10
	1-2	157	2:00	120	30,25,20,15,10,5,5,10,15,20,25,30
	1-3	267	4:00	240	30,5,30,5, . . . , 30,5,30,5
Network 2	2-1	J-196	0:00	60	5,10,15,20,15,10
	2-2	J-124	2:00	120	30,25,20,15,10,5,5,10,15,20,25,30
	2-3	J-146	4:00	240	30,5,30,5, . . . , 30,5,30,5
Network 3	3-1	J-37	0:00	60	5,10,15,20,15,10
	3-2	J-242	2:00	120	30,25,20,15,10,5,5,10,15,20,25,30
	3-3	J-56	4:00	240	30,5,30,5, . . . , 30,5,30,5

TABLE 3. Combinations of the initial number of populations (k) and the population size (m) for test instance 1-3 in Table 2

Instance	1-3-1	1-3-2	1-3-3	1-3-4	1-3-5	1-3-6	1-3-7	1-3-8	1-3-9
k	10	10	10	20	20	20	40	40	40
m	20	50	100	20	50	100	20	50	100

TABLE 4. Success rates and prediction errors of different combinations of k and m on network 1 with configuration 1-3

Instance	1-3-1	1-3-2	1-3-3	1-3-4	1-3-5	1-3-6	1-3-7	1-3-8	1-3-9
Success rate	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Error	1.55E+01	1.33E+01	1.36E+01	1.31E+01	1.30E+01	1.38E+01	1.55E+01	1.40E+01	1.41E+01

TABLE 5. Success rate of all the four algorithms in all the test cases

Algorithm	1-1	1-2	1-3	2-1	2-2	2-3	3-1	3-2	3-3
GD-ES	1	0.1	0.1	0.7	0.8	0.6	0.8	0.7	0.8
ADOT-CC(GL-SaDE)	1	0.65	0.5	1	1	0.7	1	0.9	0.4
LRM-ADOT-CC(GL-SaDE)	1	0.65	0.7	1	1	0.3	1	0.7	1
AMP-CC(GL-SaDE)	1	0.95	1	1	1	0.9	1	0.9	0.9

TABLE 6. Prediction error and standard deviation of all the four algorithms in all the test cases

Instance	GD-ES	ADOT-CC(GL-SaDE)	LRM-ADOT-CC(GL-SaDE)	AMP-CC(GL-SaDE)
1-1	7.8E+00±2.4E+00 ⁻	5.4E-02±2.3E-03 ⁻	2.7E-02±4.5E-03 ⁻	0
1-2	6.4E+00±0≈	3.6E+00±1.2E+00≈	3.5E+00±1.7E+00≈	2.6E+00±1.9E+00
1-3	1.3E+01±0≈	1.5E+01±3.2E+00≈	1.5E+01±4.2E+00≈	1.3E+01±3.0E+00
2-1	6.6E+00±1.5E+00 ⁻	8.7E-03±2.8E-04 ⁻	2.3E-02±3.3E-03 ⁻	0
2-2	9.3E+00±9.5E-01 ⁻	3.1E-02±7.5E-03 ⁻	6.2E-02±6.1E-03 ⁻	0
2-3	1.5E+01±1.4E+00≈	1.6E+01±1.7E+00≈	1.5E+01±4.2E+00≈	1.4E+01±1.3E+00
3-1	7.7E+00±2.9E+00≈	6.2E+00±2.2E+00≈	8.6E+00±1.9E+00≈	4.5E+00±2.3E+00
3-2	8.5E+00±2.3E+00≈	7.5E+00±3.8E+00≈	1.1E+01±4.3E+00≈	7.2E+00±2.6E+00
3-3	1.2E+01±1.7E+00 ⁻	1.3E-01±1.1E-02 ⁻	2.1E-01±1.8E-02 ⁻	5.4E-02±2.1E-03

TABLE 7. Results of dynamic sources over 20 runs on network 1

Run ID	Location	Error	Standard deviation
1	193 120 205 113	3.48E-02	2.94E+00
2	193 120 205 113	8.67E-02	4.80E+00
3	193 120 205 113	3.75E-02	4.63E+00
4	193 120 205 113	2.51E-02	4.46E+00
5	193 120 205 113	2.70E-02	2.70E+00
6	193 120 205 113	5.00E-02	1.85E+00
7	273 120 205 113	1.50E-01	8.26E+00
8	193 120 205 113	3.29E-02	2.89E+00
9	193 120 205 113	3.74E-02	4.02E+00
10	193 120 205 113	1.97E-02	3.17E+00
11	193 120 205 113	1.15E-02	3.31E+00
12	173 120 205 113	7.90E-02	6.37E+00
13	193 120 205 113	8.35E-02	2.36E+00
14	193 120 205 113	1.70E-02	4.37E+00
15	193 120 205 113	1.72E-02	4.43E+00
16	193 120 205 113	3.52E-02	5.75E+00
17	193 120 205 113	2.42E-02	3.36E+00
18	193 120 205 113	4.78E-02	3.54E+00
19	193 120 205 113	2.01E-02	2.28E+00
20	193 120 205 113	3.07E-02	1.80E+00

648 **List of Figures**

649	1	Framework of the adaptive multi-population method	38
650	2	The picture of three network with 97/279/430 nodes	39
651	3	The change in the number of populations and the coverage ratio on instances	
652		1-3-2/5/8	40
653	4	The change in the number of populations and the coverage ratio on instances	
654		1-3-4/5/6	41
655	5	The comparison of the number of populations (left) and the prediction error	
656		(right) obtained by the four algorithms, where a single population is used in	
657		GE-ES	42
658	6	Comparison of the change in the coverage ratio and the number of populations	
659		for the four algorithms on instances 1-3 (top) and 3-1 (bottom)	43
660	7	Solutions found by the four algorithm on instance 1-3	44
661	8	Comparison of the change in the prediction error on instance 1-3	45
662	9	The prediction error on case of dynamic contamination sources	46
663	10	Sensor concentration in the case of dynamic contamination sources	47

FIG. 1. Framework of the adaptive multi-population method

FIG. 2. The picture of three network with 97/279/430 nodes

FIG. 3. The change in the number of populations and the coverage ratio on instances 1-3-2/5/8

FIG. 4. The change in the number of populations and the coverage ratio on instances 1-3-4/5/6

FIG. 5. The comparison of the number of populations (left) and the prediction error (right) obtained by the four algorithms, where a single population is used in GE-ES

FIG. 6. Comparison of the change in the coverage ratio and the number of populations for the four algorithms on instances 1-3 (top) and 3-1 (bottom)

FIG. 7. Solutions found by the four algorithm on instance 1-3

FIG. 8. Comparison of the change in the prediction error on instance 1-3

FIG. 9. The prediction error on case of dynamic contamination sources

FIG. 10. Sensor concentration in the case of dynamic contamination sources